

GRAND.C, beyond the temporality of nodes. Digitally and physically connecting generations through product service system design, a case study

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Abstract This paper describes a case study of an early stage product service system (PSS) design. By means of a specific PSS design methodology, we were able to include insights from various domains and their underlying processes, in order to enhance value creation (beyond the product). The context of this case study was to preserve and enrich the connection between grandchildren and grandparents. Throughout the entire process, PSS design tools enable an iterative way of involving different stakeholders that broaden the exploration of recognisable emotions during a person's life and more specifically with regard to the above-mentioned node 'becoming a grandparent'. The result, GRAND.C, is an enrichment service that allows grandchildren to snoop in the past of their grandparents and is based on an authentic user experience, free play and verbal tradition. This is presented through a detailed system map and simplified customer journey, as well as a visual prototype and photo novel. It is confirmed that the prototype in particular is a very meaningful means to reinforce the design brief and to communicate the concept to the end user.

Keywords *Product service system design, Intergenerational relationships, Pleasurable experiences, Storytelling, Prototyping*

Introduction

Product Service System (PSS) design toolkit

Advancements in electronics, information and communication technology are introducing new elements to the design process and require a systematic rethinking of how designers integrate both tangible and intangible components. "PSS" can provide an opportunity to create innovative interactions between consumers, the products and services they use and the providers that offer these hybrids (Dewit & De Roeck, 2014). To support a product-service transition, the described PSS design toolkit is an ongoing collaboration (Design Flanders & Namahn, 2013; Dewit, De Roeck & Baelus, 2014; VVSG, 2013) and effort to develop a methodology, with tools and techniques (Figure 1), to design meaningful product-service systems. It includes valuable and up-to-date insights from a variety of domains and their underlying design processes: systems and systemic thinking, service design, human-centred design, interaction design, (user) experience design, product design and design thinking.

The design challenge

This research is based on the process and findings of a PSS design toolkit put to the test by 1st year master students in product development, in the context of 'nodes of life'. These landmarks of human life are

inspired by van Genep (1960), Elton and Reid (2010) and Vissers et al. (2012); e.g. leaving home, discovery and play, education, career, love, childbirth, investment, health, growing old and death.

Depending on the above-mentioned node(s), the design process runs through exploration, ideation, definition and verification, using a combination of tools specific for each phase. The goal of the project and its approach is not to seek the next large scale ecosystems, but aims to identify recognisable emotions during a person's life and to design whole product-service life cycles by means of a specific PSS design toolkit. The described project is more design-driven, with a focus on re-interpretation of meaning, rather than on performance or problem-solving (Verganti, 2009).

In this paper one specific case - GRAND.C - is highlighted in order to represent and visualise the process and usage of the PSS design toolkit, applied to the life-changing event of 'becoming a grandparent'.

Social and scientific relevance

The impact of becoming a grandparent in a lifetime is not to be underestimated. At a certain age you have to accept that your house gets invaded and you again have to take care of young children from time to time. However, an emotional bond with your grandchildren

Figure 1. Overview of the PSS tools (Design Flanders & Namahn, 2013).

is established in no time. Typically for this node is the **temporality**: “Looking back, time goes faster than you presume”.

To immerse in the theme of becoming a grandparent, an introductory literature review was undertaken in the field of **grandparent-grandchild relationships**. Partly due to demographic changes in Western societies, these relationships are posited to be more important, more intense and more prolonged than ever before, as stated in both popular and academic literature. (Bengtson, 2001; Fuller-Thomson & Minkler, 2001; Uhlenberg, 2009)

This strengthening mainly occurs during the childhood of the grandchild (Fuller-Thomson & Minkler, 2001; Uhlenberg, 2009). Noteworthy, the generation in between - the parents - can either facilitate or hinder the contact between grandparents and grandchildren. Thus, they play a key role as a lineage bridge or mediators (Kemp, 2005; Uhlenberg & Hammill, 1998). Kemp (2005) states that the importance of these mediators decreases when grandchildren grow older and more independent. Hence, as adults they keep in touch with their grandparents on their own terms.

Nevertheless before reaching adulthood, the rate of contact moments reduces when growing older (Silverstein & Long, 1998). That is why Cherlin and Furstenberg (1986) state that “the grandparent-grandchild relationship is considered to be the most intense before the grandchildren have reached adolescence”. To counteract this declination, Geurts and van Tilburg (2015) indicate that “a strong bond at an early stage of the relationship may hold back a decline in relationship intensity”. This idea of the link between the bond during childhood and adulthood is supported by three different studies (Brown, 2003; Geurts et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2005).

Building on the premise of the bond between grandparents and grandchildren that needs to be prolonged, this case study aims to motivate grandchildren to keep in touch with their grandparents more intensively. Beyond a certain age

the visits to their grandparents are perceived rather boring and obligated. Thus, once the role of the parents as mediators declines, the intrinsic motivation of the grandchildren needs to be anticipated.

The PSS design framework (Figure 2) and toolkit (Dewit & De Roeck, 2014; Dewit, 2014) follows an affective or user (experience) point of view throughout its process, inspired on research by Gemser et al. (2012) and Ruitenberg and Desmet (2012). The framework visualizes what role the three front-end domains - exploration, idea generation and definition - play in the process of integrating and designing products and services in close relation to the user experience (Dewit, 2014).

Design process

Exploration

In the first phase of the design project we are looking for a clear value constellation. With various techniques an exploration is done on the activities, actors and experiences that play a role in different stages in the event of becoming a grandparent. These insights will be translated into a ‘design challenge’.

As mentioned in the literature review, the relationship between grandparents and grandchild is more important than ever before (Bengtson, 2001). Therefore the combination of grandparents and grandchildren as the most important stakeholders is chosen to proceed into the exploration phase.

Participative and user-centred techniques (e.g. in depth interviews) served as a qualitative and interrogative research methods for exploratory purpose, enabling constant involvement of the purposive sample of six grandparents (aged 58 - 80) and four grandchildren (aged 8 - 16) throughout the entire process.

A first tool, the **Stakeholders Experience Journey** tool (Figure 3), visualises a line of well being based on their experience being either a grandparent or a grandchild. Several key moments are chosen and marked with both positive and negative feelings. These milestones were

Figure 2. PSS design framework (Dewit, 2014).

Figure 3. Stakeholders Experience Journey.

important during the interview since the interviewers could ask some more profound questions on these topics to gain insights on this special bond.

It can be stated that there is a similar evolution in the bond between grandparents and grandchildren, as they grow older. This confirms the findings from the literature research. The following three stages are recognized each time: care stage, transition stage, and problem stage.

- *The care stage is characterized by an intensive contact during regular day care and thereby a deep and unconditional connection between grandparents and young grandchildren. Grandparents are a consistent safe haven with less rules and more fun. Additionally there is an extensive communication with the parents.*
- *In the transition stage the care providing function decreases and mostly the parents are responsible for visits of the grandchildren. The contact becomes rather superficial and less personal; after all the grandchildren are too young for a spontaneous visit.*
- *Finally the grandchildren are old enough to visit their grandparents independently, but they are so busy with their own life and unintentionally forget about their grandparents. This is what we call the problem stage.*

Beside these three stages we could recognise some recurring topics in the interviews; things that several grandparents or children indicated as remarkable in their experience.

“Grandparents are the grandchild’s link to the past. Grandchildren are a grandparent’s link to the future.” (G. de Keersmaecker, personal communication, October 21, 2013)

First of all, grandparents love nothing more than to talk about their past and family history. During the interviews grandparents intend to gather various additional objects while telling their stories and soon they even show the entire house. As Kornhaber and Woodward (1981) stated, grandparents can enact several roles, an important one is being the family historian. On the other hand, both female and male grandchildren are fascinated and look up to these stories. They as well chat about those typical things you can only find at your grandparents house.

Another topic was the fact that grandparents feel a little pushed aside when their grandchildren reach a certain age. As stated before, from the transition stage on, contact becomes less intense. Grandparents grow older what makes it more difficult to keep up with their grandchildren that live their modern lives. This generation gap makes that grandparents feel like they do not know much about their grandchildren’s’ personal lives. Of course they have pictures taken at family meetings or holidays, but most of the times this kind of information comes from the parents instead of the children themselves.

To conclude the exploration phase a **Design Challenge** is formulated: what is to be designed in the next

phase? In short it could be described as ‘**blending stories**’. The goal will be to avoid the problem stage by already anticipating during the transition stage. The product service will provide an opportunity for the grandchildren to communicate with their grandparents themselves, without the parents as a necessary intermediary. The outcome needs to be convenient and intuitive in use for both parties. It should be a means to exchange personal info in an unforced way, in order to strengthen the relationship during childhood. In this way, it can be avoided that the relationship intensity declines during adolescence and adulthood.

Ideation

In the ideation phase we are working towards a viable PSS idea. Therefore we defined design requirements, emotional and rational objectives that must be met. These serve as a starting point to gather inspiration and as evaluation criteria for the different PSS scenarios that will be considered.

In the **Lotus Blossom** technique (Figure 4) we combine the eight most important requirements with inspiring examples in different contexts in order to retrieve new characteristics and ideas by means of lateral thinking.

After completing this matrix, we realised that games and play are a powerful means to transform our goals into an actual design. A typical characteristic of every child, regardless of age or gender, is curiosity. Which child can say it has never been on a treasure hunt in their grandparents’ house before? The idea is born to trigger and facilitate this explorative behaviour in order to blend the grandparents’ stories from the past with the modern environment of today’s children.

A good example of a toy that allows children to explore their environment is Sniff (Figure 5). New technologies are used without children noticing. Instead of playing games on their parents’ iPad, Sniff uses the real world as game board and can therefore be classified as a pervasive game (Johansson, 2009). In this genre new kind of gameplay experiences are created by combining different contexts and using the real world as play area to aim for physical and social interaction (Montola, Stenros & Waern, 2009).

“It is not about making society more high-tech, instead it is about making technology more social.” (CUO Social Spaces, 2012)

As observed in the exploration phase, grandparents like to show old objects to enrich their stories. It makes it easier for children to fully understand the family history. But what if some of these objects are not available anymore? What if grandparents are living in a retirement home and had to leave most of their material belongings behind? What if grandparents want to show the fun of recording an audiotape, but their recording device has stopped working long before? These kinds of questions made us think about including a service to provide the grandparents access to authentic objects that they do not possess any more themselves.

Figure 4. Lotus Blossom.

Figure 5. Sniff (Johanson, 2009).

Figure 6. Visual representation basic system GRAND.C.

The best place to find these kinds of items is of course a thrift shop. Often these stores receive these valuable objects and sell them at a low price. But of course grandparents do not mean to buy old products again. This is how we came up with the idea of a rental service for old artefacts.

With our PSS concept we want to stimulate the long lasting connection between grandparent and grandchild. In a playful way we want to encourage the discovery urge of children on the one hand, and the preservation of cultural material heritage and family stories on the other hand.

Definition

In the definition phase we aim to translate the previous statement into clear product and service attributes. The project is concluded with a design brief to finalise all front-end activities and to give a head start for new product/service development that takes the PSS concept into implementation. Specifications and architecture for both the product and the service part in the system are described as far as needed. The design brief consists of a detailed system map, which

is also translated into a simplified, graphical representation of the customer journey, a visual prototype, a photo novel to communicate the PSS concept and interactions, and finally a first working prototype.

Our PSS concept is called GRAND.C (Figure 6); an enrichment service that consists of a Basic and Advanced system. It allows grandchildren to snoop in the past of their grandparents and it is based on an authentic user experience, free play and verbal tradition.

Figure 7 shows the complexity of the **detailed system map**, which was the basis for simplifying and refining the whole concept (the complete and readable diagram can be requested from the authors). It describes the proverbial journey, emotions and interactions of the users - grandparents and grandchildren - throughout the pre service, service and post service period. It highlights the touchpoints and channels of the GRAND.C product and service, with a focus on both tangible and intangible aspects.

Figure 7. Detailed system map.

Figure 8. Customer Journey of GRAND.C Basic product system.

Because of its complexity, the scheme is also visualised in a **simplified customer journey**. The **Basic product system** (Figure 8) contains a bird (reader), tags and a birdhouse. When one or more grandchildren come over for a visit, grandparents can prepare a quest. They hide the coloured tags together with old objects of value. Through visual feedback the birds help the grandchildren to locate the different tags (Figure 9). When a tag is found, grandchildren discover a meaningful artefact and can ask their grandparents for more information. Of course the grandparents love to tell some anecdotes. Therefore the artefacts serve as a trigger to support the personal stories of the grandparents. Via GRAND.C children explore their family history in a playful way. When going home, the grandparents can pass on small mementos (e.g. the recipe of grandmother's famous pudding), which they can collect in their personal birdhouse.

Figure 10 shows the representation of the service component of the system. In collaboration with thrift

shops, GRAND.C offers an **Advanced service system** with an extensive offer of old artefacts to enrich the grandparents' stories. From all products that are brought to thrift stores by customers, GRAND.C makes a selection of the most valuable items to enhance storytelling and manages the distribution to collaborating partners. Grandparents can lend specific objects via their online user account or they can wait for the GRAND.C bus that comes to the neighbourhood every now and then. When the grandchildren's quest is completed, the objects can be returned to the nearest thrift shop.

Verification

In the final phase we address the end user again in order to verify the PSS concept. Prototypes and a photo novel are used to introduce the concept and demonstrate the interactions.

In each PSS design process it is important to verify the concept with the end user. Therefore it is necessary to have a clear representation. For the GRAND.C project

Figure 9. Visual feedback to locate tags.

Figure 10. Customer Journey of GRAND.C Advanced service system.

we made a **visual prototype** of all the tangible components of the system. This makes it much more convenient to communicate with the end user. By introducing the PSS concept to the consumer, the prototype helps to demonstrate the interactions, which is way clearer than an abstract scheme.

Due to the prototype we were able to put this front-end concept into a realistic context. We contacted two grandchildren and their grandparents from the previous **user panel** and asked them to re-enact all aspects of the scenario (Figure 11). By letting them interact with the prototype in a way that approaches reality as close as possible, we could verify which elements of the PSS concept work well and which ones do not work as planned, before scaling up. The most important aspect to be tested is the value constellation: Do the children have fun during the game and is the game encouraging the grandparents to bring up personal stories that are fascinating the grandchildren?

The setting was the house of the grandparents, which is a familiar environment where the participants are at ease. The grandparents were asked to hide some tags with objects that they value. Because the prototype was not actually working, we helped the children to locate the tags by playing the classic hot and cold game combined with some other game mechanics. When a tag was found, the grandparents took some time to provide the children with several background stories.

In the next round some other game mechanics were included such as competing against each other, varieties in difficulty and other ways of searching, as these will also be present in the real GRAND.C game. In reality the different colours of tags will represent different levels with evolving kinds of visual feedback that will get harder to interpret.

This re-enacting of the scenario gave us the opportunity to capture every moment in the customer journey and make a detailed photo novel to communicate the total concept to the end user. By watching this novella, the user can easily empathize with the story, which makes it possible for us to gather feedback on all aspects of the product service system.

This verification method gave us confirmation of the capability of GRAND.C to turn a regular visit into a valuable moment of interaction between two generations. The game creates a pleasurable moment for the children but in the end it is just the medium to stimulate that special relationship between grandparents and grandchildren which they will value both significantly in the long term. Additionally, society will benefit from GRAND.C as well, since the preservation of an important aspect of cultural heritage is supported

In order to further evaluate the game mechanics, we made a second prototype of the bird (Figure 12), provided with real-time visual feedback to locate a tag. Here, we aimed to implement electronics without losing the aesthetic qualities of the first prototype. By using two Bluetooth modules, coded in Arduino, we were able to put the received signals in different ranges and make it possible to distinguish distances. This input is converted into visual feedback; the closer the bird approaches a tag, the more lights will go on.

With this prototype we could conduct another user test with less interference of the researchers. Figure 13 shows a participant using the bird to search a tag. Finally the prototype was showcased at 'Buzzkruit' Expo in Antwerp, where visitors could try out the game and react to the concept (Figure 14). On this link below a video can be found where the concept is explained (in Dutch) as well as a quick demonstration of the prototype: <https://vimeo.com/135117515>

Figure 11. Scenario re-enacting.

Figure 12. Electronic prototype.

Figure 13. User test with electronic prototype.

Figure 14. GRAND.C exposed at Buzzkruit.

The concept of GRAND.C can be assessed through the PSS strategy and typology. Tukker and Tischner (2006) distinguished eight different PSS categories, going from Product Oriented to Result Oriented (Figure 15). GRAND.C consists of two components with each a different focus. The Basic product system can be situated in the category of a **Product related service**. The bird readers, tags and bird houses are sold as a product, but are combined with a product related service. This Advanced service system of GRAND.C concerns the collecting and lending of valuable artefacts through the GRAND.C bus and thrift stores. Therefore it can be positioned in the category of **Product renting**, which is more Use Oriented.

Discussion and future research

The context of grandparents and grandchildren is one almost everyone can relate to. Nevertheless the product service system (PSS) tools, which combines a variety of existing perspectives (such as human-centred design), provided a structured framework to indulge in this node of life and gain new insights during the exploration and ideation phase, with a clear focus on the service aspect of PSS. Especially the

tools where interaction with the stakeholders was required, gave us the opportunity to get inspired by the personal anecdotes of our test users. Each one of their unique experiences triggered some out of the box thinking.

We noticed that the first PSS tools (during the exploration phase) are rather focused on 'words' such as the Design Challenge and Requirements. Yet, from these concepts we reached a turning point with the Lotus Blossom. The design process suddenly became more visual and tangible through the use of inspirational examples that could meet the requirements. It helped us to translate the needs and wishes to attributes and interactions.

More opportunities for the PSS design toolkit lie in adding useful and diverse techniques supporting the definition and verification phase. PSS design is situated in the front end of innovation and aims for a valid concept. Therefore the outcome should be verified with the end consumer and communicated in an understandable manner.

Conclusion

In this PSS design assignment we did not aim for solving big problems concerning grandparents and grandchildren. By using the PSS design toolkit we could focus on exploring the whole context and the emotions that occur during the event of becoming a grandparent. After a literature review and primary research we discovered that from a certain age, visits to the grandparents are reduced to occasional, rather dull events. Here, we saw an opportunity to anticipate this stage by creating a stronger connection between the two different generations before the children reach adolescence and are fully occupied with their own lives.

The outcome of the design process is GRAND.C, a PSS concept to stimulate a long lasting connection between grandparent and grandchild. The product system offers a game for children to go on a treasure hunt in their grandparents' house and explore their family history in a playful way. The service component allows grandparents to rent other valuable objects to extend the possibilities of telling interesting stories.

As this design case is situated in the front end of innovation, the design process did not result in a 'final' product, but in a detailed system map where all interactions and touchpoints are described. However it is important to define the whole system in order to proceed in the stage of New Product/Service Development, this kind of scheme is not useful to verify the concept with the end user.

By introducing the prototype to a user panel and re-enacting the prescribed scenario, we could verify the capability of GRAND.C to evoke stories and the willingness of grandchildren to hear these stories and explore their family history.

We succeeded in designing a product service system that fits into the PSS strategy. The specific case study of GRAND.C can be situated in the PSS model as a rather product focused concept. The tangible objects (bird and tags) have a significant role. As stated by Dewit and De Roeck (2014): "Without a dedicated product the PSS cannot exist. The product carries specific aesthetic qualities and allows embedding emotion, personal meaning in the product".

However, the service component allows the eco-system to be longer involved with the customer. The user experience does not end after playing the GRAND.C game, it can proceed much longer since the GRAND.C service constantly introduces new objects that evoke new stories every time. Thus combining both product and service components in one system results into a better user experience that lasts longer.

It can be stated that GRAND.C provides a pleasurable moment for both grandparents and grandchildren when the game is played. The game is a means to create a stronger connection on the long term that both parties will significantly benefit. Additionally GRAND.C supports the preservation of important cultural heritage. With all these ingredients, GRAND.C reconnects two generations digitally and physically in

order to look beyond the temporality of this special node of life.

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